

Summary of results of NSN and IRON evaluation against BB, kresek, and SR, Haryana, India.

Year	Trial	Test	Severity index	Entries (no.) showing rating							Total entries (no.)	
				1	2	3	4	5	7	9		
1980	NSN-I	BB	6.6	High	1	—	26 ^a	—	28	180	33	268
	NSN-II				—	—	12	—	18	154	92	276
1981	NSN-I	Kresek	6.9	High	32	—	12	—	72	49	157	321
	IRON	BB	7.4	High	1	—	26	—	21	67	137	254
1982	NSN-I	BB	5.4	Moderate	39	—	69	—	68	106	54	334
		Kresek	5.8	Moderate	—	—	6	—	206	104	11	327
	IRON	SR	4.0	High	4	23	79	71	158	—	—	330
		BB	7.0	High	3	—	35	—	38	93	133	343

^aEntries resistant for more than 2 yr — NSN (resistant to BB and K): IET nos. 7061, 7100, 7338, 7349, 7393, 7419, 7420, 7421, 7431, 7434, 7447, 7662, 7707, 7736, 7752, 7753. IRON (resistant to BB): BR161-2B-53, BR161-2B-58, BR171-2B-8, IR134-20-6-3-3-1, IR19660-131-3-3-3, IR9763-11-2-2-3, IR17488-2-3-2, IR19661-23-3-2-2, IR17494-32-1-1-3-2, IR75-2878, IR50, IR54, DR55-9, MRC 603-383. NSN entries resistant to SR and BB for 2 yr: IET nos. 7753, 8169, 8175, 8195, 8197, 8259, 8303, 8319, 8322, 8325, 8327. NSN entries resistant to SR, kresek, and BB (1982): IET nos. 8140, 8145, 8353, 4141.

2-2-3, IR17488-2-3-2, IR19661-23-3-2-2, IR17494-32-1-1-3-2, and MRC603-383 were included in advanced breeding trials. In the NSN, 11 entries were resistant to SR and BB and 4 (IET8140, IET8145, IET8353, and IET4141) to SR, kresek, and BB. □

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Pest control and management INSECTS

Inheritance of virulence of the North Sumatra population of the brown planthopper (BPH) on IR42

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We studied the genetic nature of virulence of the North Sumatra (NS) BPH population. Nymphal development and adult longevity and maturity of the NS population, the Bogor population on Pelita I/1 that does not infest resistant rices, and their hybrid progenies were compared on IR42 seedlings.

The F₁ and F₂ hybrid progenies were obtained by heterogametic pairing of the NS and Bogor BPH populations. The backcrossed progenies were bred by crossing the F₁ with the NS or the Bogor population. Twenty 1st-instar nymphs and newly emerged brachypterous adult females were collected at random from each parental or hybrid population maintained on susceptible Pelita I/1, and placed in test tubes with 1- to 2-wk-old IR42 seedlings, 2 seedlings/tube. Nymphal development, and longevity and development of ovaries were recorded

Table 1. Nymphal development of the NS and Bogor populations and their hybrid progenies on IR42 seedlings, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Cross ^a	Nymphs tested (no.)	Adult emergence (%)	Developmental period of nymphs which became adults (d ± SD)	Growth index ^b
Female × Male				
NS × NS	20	80	12.9 ± 1.3	6.2
B × B	20	20	15.5 ± 0.6	1.3
NS × B	20	30	14.3 ± 1.5	2.1
B × NS	20	10	14.5 ± 2.1	0.7
(NS × B) ²	20	30	13.3 ± 0.5	2.3
(B × NS) ²	19	21	12.8 ± 1.0	1.6
NS (NS × B)	20	55	13.4 ± 2.4	4.1
B (B × NS)	20	35	14.4 ± 2.6	2.4

^aNS = North Sumatra population on IR42, B = Bogor population on Pelita I/1. ^b% adult emergence divided by mean duration of nymphal period in d.

Table 2. Longevity and maturity of adult females of the NS and Bogor populations and their hybrid progenies on IR42 seedlings, Jakarta, Indonesia.

Cross ^a	Females tested (no.)	Gravid females (%)	Longevity (d ± S. D.)
Female × Male			
NS × NS	20	90	16.0 ± 6.7
B × B	21	5	3.6 ± 2.7
NS × B	20	5	3.9 ± 4.0
B × NS	17	18	5.5 ± 6.1
(NS × B) ²	20	30	6.5 ± 5.8
(B × NS) ²	20	10	4.3 ± 4.5
NS (NS × B)	20	50	12.5 ± 9.5
B (B × NS)	20	25	6.3 ± 5.8

^aSee footnote, Table 1.

daily. Experiments were conducted at room temperature (25-30°C).

Parentage distinctly influenced nymphal development. Eight percent of the NS nymphs emerged as adults in 13 d. Only 20% of the Bogor population reached adulthood in 16 d. Development of the hybrid F₁ and F₂ nymphs from reciprocal crosses was similar to that of the Bogor population. When the F₁ with NS as maternal parent was backcrossed with the same population, nymphal development was intermediate between the NS and Bogor populations. However,

backcrossing to the Bogor population did not improve nymphal development on the resistant variety (Table 1).

Newly emerged females of any parental or hybrid population placed on IR42 seedlings clearly fell into two discontinuous classes: one that became gravid and survived significantly longer

(17.2 d), and another that quickly died (survived 3.5 d).

Of the NS population, 90% of the females became gravid and survived about 18 d on IR42 seedlings. Most Bogor females died within 5 d. In the hybrid F₁ and F₂ progenies, 5-30% females became gravid with 4-7 d average longevity. Back-

crossing the F₁ hybrid and the NS population increased the parentage of gravid females, but backcrossing with the Bogor population had no such effect (Table 2).

The results indicated that the NS population's ability to infest IR42 is inherited from recessive genes when interbred with avirulent BPH populations. □

Possible genetic isolation between the *Leersia* and rice brown planthopper (BPH)

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It was reported that the *Leersia*-feeding BPH found on *Leersia hexandra* in North Sumatra is morphologically indistinguishable from the rice BPH *Nilaparvata lugens*, but distinctive from each other by their incompatible host requirements. To determine possible genetic barriers, we examined courtship reaction and crossability of the populations.

Courtship reactions were observed by a seedling bridge method. A pre-mating male and a female, 4 to 5 d old, were separately placed at the base of 2 rice seedlings about 10 cm apart in a 17 × 25 cm jar. The leaf blades touched to enable the BPH to communicate by seedling transmitted courtship signals.

When a male and female from the same population were tested, the male moved to the female on the other seedling and they successfully mated. Homogametic matings usually occurred within 4-5 min. Heterogametic matings between the *Leersia*- and rice-BPH seldom occurred except when the male and female met by chance through random wandering.

To confirm our results, mating choice experiments were conducted using a similar method, but three seedlings were set at triangular positions with crossed leaf blades. In one test, a single rice-BPH female was placed on one of the three seedlings and one male each of *Leersia*- and rice-BPH were placed separately on each of the two other seedlings. Only the male rice-BPH reacted and mated with the female within an average 5 min. The male *Leersia*-BPH did not react. In another test, a single male *Leersia*-BPH was allowed to select between *Leersia*- and rice-BPH females. The male always moved to and mated with the female

Leersia-BPH within 4 min. Communication by acoustic courtship signals is not successful between the *Leersia*- and rice-BPH.

Despite failure in courtship communication, *Leersia*- and rice-BPH can mate and produce viable hybrid progeny if confined on the same plant. However, the hybrid progenies were poorly adapted to both host plants. Percentage of adult emergence of the F₁ BPH hybrids were 8-26 on both hosts (see table). The F₂ population also was viable, and survived better than the F₁ on the same host.

We conclude that *Leersia*- and rice-BPH are noninterbreeding sympatric populations. Genetic interchanges between them are greatly restricted by unsuccessful courtship communication, incompatible host plant preference, and breakdown of host affinity in hybrid progenies. □

Adult emergence of the *Leersia*- and rice-BPH, and their F₁ and F₂ hybrids on rice and *L. hexandra*, Jakarta, Indonesia.^a

Cross ^b (♀ × ♂)	Host	No. of adults emerged				% adult emergence
		MF	BF	MM	BM ^c	
L × L	Rice	0	0	0	0	0
	<i>Leersia</i>	0	21	1	24	92
R × R	Rice	0	29	6	12	94
	<i>Leersia</i>	0	0	0	0	0
L × R	Rice	0	7	1	3	22
	<i>Leersia</i>	3	2	0	8	26
R × L	Rice	2	3	3	2	20
	<i>Leersia</i>	1	0	3	0	8
(L × R) ^{2d}	Rice	1	6	3	1	22
	<i>Leersia</i>	10	4	4	1	38
(R × L) ^{2d}	Rice	7	16	9	13	90
	<i>Leersia</i>	9	0	9	0	36

^aFifty first instar nymphs were used for each test. Number of adults emerged was recorded 22 days after introduction of the nymphs. ^bL = *Leersia*-BPH, R = rice - BPH. ^cMF = macropterous female, BF = brachypterous female, MM = macropterous male, BM = brachypterous male. ^dAdults emerged on *L. hexandra* and Pelita I/1 were used, respectively.

Monitoring brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes by rice garden in North Sumatra

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Monitoring BPH biotype nature or virulence is important in variety-oriented BPH management. To monitor BPH biotypes and forecast population surges, we designed a rice garden in which several rice varieties are planted separately in 5- × 5-m plots in a randomized block design.

In Deli Serdang, North Sumatra, in 1983 dry season, we used that technique